

The Meissner effect in superconductors: emergence versus reductionism

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The Meissner effect, the expulsion of magnetic field from the interior of a metal entering the superconducting state, is arguably the most fundamental property of superconductors, discovered in 1933. The conventional theory of superconductivity developed in 1957 is generally believed to fully explain the Meissner effect. We will review the arguments that support this consensus, rooted in the concept of emergence. However, recent work has shown that there are questions related to momentum conservation in the process of magnetic field expulsion that have not been addressed within the conventional theory. Within a reductionist approach, it has been proposed that those questions can only be resolved by introducing physics that is not part of the conventional theory, namely that there is *radial motion of electric charge* in the transition process. This is consistent with the behavior of classical plasmas, where motion of magnetic field lines is always associated with motion of charges. We review how this approach explains puzzles associated with momentum transfer between electrons and ions in the Meissner effect. Whether or not radial charge motion is associated with the Meissner effect has fundamental implications regarding superconductivity mechanisms in materials and regarding strategies to search for new materials with higher superconducting transition temperatures. Therefore, adjudication of this question is urgent and important.

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The two most characteristic properties of superconductors are zero resistance and the Meissner effect, the expulsion of magnetic fields from the interior of a material becoming superconducting. The Meissner effect is the property that differentiates superconductors from “perfect conductors”, which are materials that conduct electricity with no resistance but do not expel magnetic fields. Perfect conductors do not exist, but can be regarded as a limiting case of “very good conductors”, that do exist. What makes superconductors *qualitatively* different from very good or perfect conductors is precisely the Meissner effect. When the effect was experimentally discovered in 1933 [1] it triggered a very rapid advance in the field, because it was completely unexpected and because it is such a fundamental property. We can reasonably expect that such a fundamental property of superconductors should reflect fundamental physics underlying the superconductivity phenomenon. What that fundamental physics is is currently under contention and is the subject of this review.

It is generally believed in the scientific community that the Meissner effect is explained by the conventional theory of superconductivity, BCS [2–4]. And even for unconventional theories proposed to describe what are believed to be “unconventional superconductors” [5] not described by BCS, it is believed that the Meissner effect is explained by the same principles that explain it in the conventional theory. This conventional understanding of the Meissner effect characterizes it as an emergent property of the systems [6, 7], and does not address in detail processes and mechanisms involved in the Meissner effect. In essence, it postulates that the physical systems will find ways to reach their lowest energy states. Instead, in recent years an alternative reductionist approach has emerged [8], which asks and proposes detailed answers to how phenomena associated with the Meissner effect occur, and requires specific properties of the physical systems, in the absence of which the Meissner effect would not take place.

The basic principles that govern the Meissner effect that I will discuss here within both alternative points of view should be understandable to a broad audience of physicists with no specialized background in the theory of superconductivity. Which one is correct, if any, is unknown, and has fundamental implications for the future advancement in the understanding of superconductivity and its practical applications.

II. WHAT THE MEISSNER EFFECT IS AND IS NOT

It is often said that the Meissner effect is the *exclusion* of magnetic fields from the interior of superconducting materials [9]. It is also often said, in describing experiments where a material is first cooled into the superconducting state and then a magnetic field is applied, that the superconductor *expelled* the magnetic field [10]. Both statements are wrong, and it is worth emphasizing it here at the outset because these misconceptions are pervasive in the literature and muddle the essential issue. Certainly the conventional theory of superconductivity can explain the Meissner effect as described in this paragraph. But that is *not* the Meissner effect.

The Meissner effect is *not* the state of a superconductor, even if superconductors with magnetic field excluded are often said to be in the “Meissner state”. The Meissner effect (Fig. 1) is the *process of expulsion* of a pre-existent magnetic field from the interior of a metal that is initially in the normal state and transits into the superconducting state, that occurs either when the temperature is lowered or the external magnetic field is lowered. In this paper we will consider only type I superconductors, where the expulsion of magnetic field occurs suddenly at given values of temperature and magnetic field. Instead, in type II superconductors the expulsion of magnetic fields occurs over a finite range of temperature or magnetic field. In this paper we want to understand the

FIG. 1: Graphic depiction of the Meissner effect from Meissner and Heidenreich’s 1936 paper [12].

Meissner effect: what is the physics that gives rise to the *process* whereby the material goes from its initial normal state with magnetic field in the interior to its final superconducting state with magnetic field excluded. To understand the process it is not sufficient to describe the equilibrium properties of the superconductor in no matter how much detail, as is often done.

III. THE MEISSNER-OSCHENFELD DISCOVERY, AND WHY IT TOOK SO LONG

The discovery of the Meissner effect was entirely accidental and entirely unexpected. Meissner and Ochsenfeld in early 1933 designed an experiment to test a calculation performed by Laue and Möglich [11] on the expected change in the current distribution in a wire transitioning between normal and superconducting states. To do so, they circulated current in two parallel wires in opposite direction and measured the magnetic field in the region between the wires. In one of several measurements they found the surprising result that the measured magnetic field was different when the directions of the currents were switched. This was interpreted by Meissner to imply that the difference originated in the earth’s magnetic field, that had not been compensated for in that particular measurement, and hence indicated that a change in magnetic field in the neighborhood of the wires would also occur in the absence of applied current [12]. Indeed, subsequent experiments performed without current circulating through the wires confirmed the expectation, implying that the earth’s magnetic field had been expelled from the interior of the superconducting wires. They immediately realized the importance of their accidental discovery and published a short note in October 1933 titled

“Ein neuer Effekt bei Eintritt der Supraleitfähigkeit”, “A new effect at the onset of superconductivity”, where they explicitly stated (guessed?) that their results implied that the diamagnetic susceptibility became exactly $-1/4\pi$ in the superconducting state, implying complete expulsion of the magnetic field. Meissner described in detail the experimental process that led to the discovery in a later publication in 1936 together with F. Heidenreich [12].

The result was particularly surprising in view of Lippmann’s theorem [13], of which Meissner was very much aware of [12], that stated that when a normal conductor in the presence of a magnetic field is cooled and becomes a perfect conductor no change in magnetic field should take place in accordance with Maxwell’s equations. There is no indication that neither Meissner nor any other superconductivity researcher at the time doubted the validity of Lippmann’s theorem. In fact, that is presumably the reason for why it took so long, 22 years, from the discovery of superconductivity in 1911 to the discovery of the Meissner effect. It follows that if Meissner and Ochsenfeld had taken the precaution to shield the earth’s magnetic field from their apparatus with a Helmholtz coil in order to accurately test the Laue-Möglich theoretical prediction without confounding factors, which in fact they had done in other experiments at the time [12], the Meissner effect would not have been discovered.

The short Meissner-Ochsenfeld paper [1] contained no figures. A graphical depiction of the Meissner effect was first given by Meissner in his 1936 paper [12], reproduced here in Fig. 1.

IV. THE KEESOM EXPERIMENTS

Immediately after the Meissner effect was discovered it became clear that it had profound implications. Namely, that the equilibrium state of a superconductor in a magnetic field was independent of its history, contrary to what had been thought before, and that the superconducting state is an equilibrium thermodynamic state of matter to which the laws of thermodynamics apply. This was clearly brought to light in the work of Gorter [14, 15] and Gorter and Casimir [16]. In particular, it implied that under carefully controlled conditions the normal-superconductor transition in the presence of a magnetic field is a *reversible phase transformation* with no change in the entropy of the universe, just as any other first order phase transition such as water-ice or water-vapor.

This however raised a puzzling question - not in the mind of theorists that were happy applying the Clausius-Clapeyron formalism of other first-order phase transformations to the normal-superconductor transition without any qualms, but in the mind of a very thoughtful experimentalist: Willem Henrik Keesom.

Keesom realized, even if he did not state it explicitly in his papers, that there is a fundamental difference between

any other first order phase transition and the superconducting transition in a magnetic field: in the latter, the system carries *momentum* in one of the phases and does not in the other.

A superconductor in a magnetic field has a surface current that carries mechanical momentum. When it makes a transition to the normal state the supercurrent stops and its momentum is gone. Where does the momentum go, and how, and what does it imply?

In a series of papers between 1934 and 1938 [17–21] Keesom and coworkers performed careful experiments measuring thermal and magnetic properties of superconductors in a magnetic field undergoing transitions to and from the superconducting state with the purpose of establishing experimentally whether or not the transition was a reversible phase transformation, as theory [14–16] said it was. In particular, whether any Joule heat was generated when the system went normal and the supercurrent stopped. They established quantitatively that indeed to high accuracy no Joule heat is dissipated when the transition occurs very slowly, implying that the theoretical description as a reversible phase transformation is indeed correct [21, 22].

Why did Keesom spend so much time and effort in establishing experimentally what seemed obvious from a theoretical point of view? Presumably because, unlike others, he realized how profoundly counterintuitive it was that a supercurrent, with current density much higher than in normal metallic conductors, could stop in the phase transformation to a resistive state without any dissipation of Joule heat. As he stated emphatically in one of his papers [18], “*it is essential that the persistent currents have been annihilated before the material gets resistance, so that no Joule heat is developed*”. He did not venture to hypothesize how this could happen, but deserves the credit for having posed this fundamental question, which surprisingly nobody else paid attention to until many years later [23].

V. THERMODYNAMICS OF THE MEISSNER EFFECT

The thermodynamics of the Meissner effect is well understood [2–4, 14–16]. I will review it briefly here because it is essential to its understanding.

We consider a long cylindrical superconductor of length ℓ and radius R , inside a solenoid through which a constant current I circulates, driven by a power source, as shown in the lower left inset of Fig. 2, giving rise to a uniform field H . The current is given by

$$I = \frac{c}{4\pi} \ell H \quad (1)$$

by Ampere’s law. We assume that $H = H_c(T_1)$, the thermodynamic critical field at temperature T_1 . When the system is cooled from the normal into the superconducting state, point 1 to point 1’ in Fig. 2, both infinitesimally close to T_1 , the magnetic field is expelled from

FIG. 2: Critical field versus temperature for a type I superconductor. The applied external field is $H = H_c(T_1)$. The points **1** and **1'** are at temperatures infinitesimally above and below T_1 . The Meissner effect is the expulsion of magnetic flux as the system makes the transition from point **1** to point **1'**. $L(T_1)$ is the latent heat released by the body when it makes the transition from the normal to the superconducting state at temperature T_1 . The lower left inset shows the superconducting sample in a solenoid powered by a battery that delivers a constant current I (Eq. (1)).

its interior. This means that a current I circulates near the surface of the superconductor in opposite direction to that of the solenoid.

During the process of field expulsion a Faraday counter-emf is generated that opposes the flux expulsion, given by

$$\epsilon = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{d\phi}{dt} \quad (2)$$

with ϕ the magnetic flux through the superconductor. The Faraday electric field points in the same direction as the current of the solenoid that keeps the external magnetic field constant, therefore it delivers energy to the power source. The energy per unit time delivered to the power source during the transition is

$$P = \frac{dW}{dt} = \epsilon I = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{d\phi}{dt} \left(\frac{c}{4\pi} \ell H \right) \quad (3)$$

and the total energy delivered to the power source as the flux through the sample changes from $\phi(t=0) = \pi R^2 H$ to zero is

$$W = \frac{H^2}{4\pi} V \quad (4)$$

with $V = \pi R^2 \ell$ the volume of the sample. From now on we will assume $V = 1$ for simplicity.

Half of that energy, $H^2/(8\pi)$, is the energy of the magnetic field that was in the volume of the sample, and the other half is the lowering of the energy of the sample in going from the normal to the superconducting state. In addition, a latent heat $L(T_1) = T_1(S_n(T_1) - S_s(T_1))$ is

released by the sample into a heat bath at the same temperature, where S_n and S_s are the entropies of the normal and superconducting states. The change in energy of the sample in going from the normal to the superconducting state is

$$U_n - U_s = \frac{H_c(T_1)^2}{8\pi} + T_1(S_n(T_1) - S_s(T_1)) \quad (5)$$

and in terms of the free energies ($F = U - TS$) we have

$$F_n - F_s = \frac{H_c(T_1)^2}{8\pi}. \quad (6)$$

We have ignored the fact that the current in the superconductor circulates not right at the surface but on a surface layer of thickness λ_L , the London penetration depth, under the assumption that $\lambda_L \ll R$, the radius of the cylinder.

This thermodynamic understanding implies that the total change in the entropy of the universe is zero in the transition process [24]. This requires that the transition happens infinitely slowly so that no Joule heat is generated [25]. This requires that the points **1** and **1'** in Fig. 2 are infinitely close.

VI. HOW LONDON ELECTRODYNAMICS EXPLAINS THE MEISSNER EFFECT

Let us review briefly the London brothers' F. and H. London description of the Meissner effect [26–28], which it is often said explains the Meissner effect [29, 30], even though it does not. Starting with Newton's equation for the velocity of an electron of mass m_e and charge e under an electric field \vec{E}

$$m_e \frac{d\vec{v}_s}{dt} = e\vec{E} \quad (7)$$

gives for the current density $\vec{J} = n_s e \vec{v}_s$, with n_s the density of superconducting carriers,

$$\frac{\partial \vec{J}}{\partial t} = \frac{n_s e^2}{m_e} \vec{E} \quad (8)$$

and applying the curl on both sides and using Faraday's law $\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -(1/c) \partial \vec{B} / \partial t$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{J} = -\frac{n_s e^2}{m_e c} \frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \quad (9)$$

Integrating with respect to time, and assuming as initial conditions no magnetic field and no current yields

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{J} = -\frac{n_s e^2}{m_e c} \vec{B} = -\frac{c}{4\pi \lambda_L^2} \vec{B} \quad (10)$$

which is the celebrated London equation, with

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_L^2} \equiv \frac{4\pi n_s e^2}{m_e c^2} \quad (11)$$

giving the London penetration depth λ_L . From Eq. (10) and Ampere's law it follows that $\nabla^2 \vec{B} = (1/\lambda_L^2) \vec{B}$ which implies that the magnetic field only penetrates a distance λ_L into the superconductor, i.e. is excluded from its interior.

Of course under the initial conditions appropriate for the Meissner effect, $\vec{J}(\vec{r}, t=0) = 0$ and $\vec{B}(\vec{r}, t=0) = \vec{B}_0$, time integration of Eq. (9) yields instead of Eq. (10)

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{J} = -\frac{c}{4\pi\lambda_L^2} (\vec{B} - \vec{B}_0) \quad (12)$$

with solution $\vec{J}(\vec{r}, t) = 0$ and $\vec{B}(\vec{r}, t) = \vec{B}_0$ at all times, therefore the initial magnetic field is unchanged, no supercurrent is generated and there is no Meissner effect.

The London brothers *postulated* [26, 27] that Eq. (10) describes the state of the superconductor *independent of initial conditions*. In particular, that the system would reach the state described by Eq. (10) and not by Eq. (12) when cooled from the normal state into the superconducting state in the presence of magnetic field \vec{B}_0 . The London brothers did not explain what would be the physical reason for the material cooled in the presence of \vec{B}_0 to ignore Eq. (12) and instead be governed by Eq. (10). This is still widely misunderstood today [29, 30].

For the purpose of later discussion, we rewrite London's Eq. (10) in terms of the superfluid velocity as

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{v}_s = -\frac{e}{m_e c} \vec{B} \quad (13)$$

or, in terms of the magnetic vector potential \vec{A}

$$\vec{v}_s = -\frac{e}{m_e c} \vec{A} \quad (14)$$

where we are assuming, following London [28], that \vec{A} obeys the Coulomb gauge $\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{A} = 0$.

VII. HOW BCS THEORY EXPLAINS THE MEISSNER EFFECT

BCS theory [2–4] shows that for a system of electrons that interact via a net attractive interaction the ground state wavefunction is of the form

$$|\Psi_{BCS}\rangle = \prod_k (u_k^2 + v_k^2 c_{k\uparrow}^\dagger c_{-k\downarrow}^\dagger) |0\rangle. \quad (15)$$

where $c_{k\sigma}^\dagger$ creates an electron of spin σ in the single particle state of crystal momentum k , and u_k and v_k are complex amplitudes determined by minimization of the energy. BCS showed that the state Eq. (15) has a lower energy than the normal metal Fermi sea. In the presence of a magnetic field H this remains true up to a critical value of the magnetic field H_c that satisfies

$$E_n - E_s = \frac{H_c^2}{8\pi} \quad (16)$$

where E_n is the energy of the normal state with magnetic field in its interior and E_s is the energy of the superconducting state described by the wavefunction Eq. (15) that does not allow a magnetic field in the interior. The treatment extends to finite temperatures, leading to the condition Eq. (6) that determines that if the system is in an applied field $H = H_c(T_1)$ it will have lower free energy when $T > T_1$ if it is in the normal state with the magnetic field in its interior and it will have lower free energy when $T < T_1$ if it is in the superconducting state with the magnetic field excluded from the interior.

That is one reason for why it is said that BCS theory predicts and explains the Meissner effect. However the argument is flawed. It is not a fact that if the system is initially in the normal state at $T > T_1$ and its temperature is lowered to $T < T_1$ it necessarily will evolve to its lowest free energy state. It will if there is a physical mechanism for it to do so. If there isn't, it will stay in the initial state, or it may evolve to another state that is not the lowest free energy state. The fact that in experiments under field-cooling conditions the final state invariably has some magnetic field trapped [31–33] indicates that lowest free energy alone is not a valid criterion to decide where the system will evolve. It is necessary to understand the *physical processes* that determine how the system goes from the initial to the final state to understand which final state(s) can be reached. BCS theory doesn't do that.

Another argument that is used to argue that BCS theory predicts the Meissner effect is the following: the canonical momentum of a superfluid electron is

$$\vec{p} = m_e \vec{v}_s + \frac{e}{c} \vec{A} \quad (17)$$

According to BCS theory the canonical momentum of superfluid electrons in a simply connected sample is $\vec{p} = 0$. Setting $\vec{p} = 0$ in Eq. (17) yields the London equation Eq. (14), that predicts that no magnetic field exists in the interior of the superconductor.

The problem with this argument is of course that it does not address the question of how the system evolves from the normal state with a magnetic field in the interior to reach the final state where $\vec{p} = 0$. In more detail, in the normal state there is a uniform magnetic field \vec{B}_0 in the interior of the sample with magnetic vector potential

$$\vec{A}(\vec{r}, t=0) = \frac{\vec{B}_0 \times \vec{r}}{2} \quad (18)$$

and superfluid velocity $\vec{v}_s = 0$, so that the canonical momentum is

$$\vec{p}(\vec{r}, t=0) = \frac{e}{c} \vec{A}(\vec{r}, t=0) \quad (19)$$

and how the system evolves to the final state characterized by $\vec{p}(\vec{r}, t) = 0$ is not described.

More generally, BCS theory, as well as the associated Bogoliubov-de-Gennes theory [4] to treat

spatially-dependent situations, and the phenomenological Ginzburg-Landau theory introduced several years earlier [34], imply that the state of the superconductor can be described by a *macroscopic wavefunction*

$$\psi(\vec{r}) = |\psi(\vec{r})|e^{i\theta(\vec{r})} \quad (20)$$

where the amplitude of the wavefunction is the square root of the superfluid density $n_s(\vec{r})$, $|\psi(\vec{r})| = n_s(\vec{r})^{1/2}$, and the phase of the superfluid wavefunction is related to the superfluid velocity through the equation

$$\hbar\vec{\nabla}\theta(\vec{r}) = m_e\vec{v}_s(\vec{r}) + \frac{e}{c}\vec{A}(\vec{r}) \quad (21)$$

which yields the London Eq. (13) upon taking the curl of both sides of Eq. (21). This ‘proof’ applies also to multiply connected samples. But again, the problem is that in the initial stage of the Meissner effect the system in the normal state is *not* described by the wavefunction Eq. (20), and how the system evolves in time to reach the final state described by Eq. (20) that excludes the magnetic field is not explained by Ginzburg-Landau theory, contrary to what textbooks say [35].

There has been some work extending the Ginzburg-Landau description to time-dependent situations, the so-called time-dependent Ginzburg Landau theory (TDGL) [36, 37], and this formalism has been used to describe the normal-superconductor transition in a magnetic field [38, 39]. In TDGL theory it is assumed that the time-dependent superconducting order parameter $\psi(\vec{r}, t)$ relaxes exponentially to its equilibrium value in a non-equilibrium situation. The formalism involves a first order differential equation in time with *real* coefficients for the time evolution of the order parameter. Hence it describes *irreversible* time evolution, and is therefore not relevant to the Meissner effect for type I superconductors, which is a *reversible* process under ideal conditions. In addition, recent work has shown mathematically [40, 41] that this assumption of TDGL theory is incorrect and that within BCS-Bogoliubov-de-Gennes theory the superconducting order parameter will *not* relax spontaneously to its equilibrium value.

Another argument claimed to explain the Meissner effect within BCS theory, already given in the original paper [2], starts from the system in the BCS state Eq. (15) and calculates the linear response of the system to an applied magnetic field defined by vector potential \vec{A} . The perturbing Hamiltonian is

$$H_1 = \frac{ie\hbar}{2mc} \sum_i (\vec{\nabla}_i \cdot \vec{A} + \vec{A} \cdot \vec{\nabla}_i) \quad (22)$$

This perturbation causes the BCS wavefunction $|\Psi_{BCS}\rangle$ to become, to first order in \vec{A}

$$|\Psi\rangle = |\Psi_{BCS}\rangle - \sum_n \frac{\langle \Psi_n | H_1 | \Psi_{BCS} \rangle}{E_n} |\Psi_n\rangle \quad (23)$$

where $|\Psi_n\rangle$ are states obtained from the BCS state $|\Psi_{BCS}\rangle$ by exciting 2 quasiparticles, and E_n is the excitation energy. The expectation value of the current

operator \vec{J}_{op} with this wave function gives the electric current \vec{J} and the calculation yields [2, 3]:

$$\vec{J} = \langle \Psi | \vec{J}_{op} | \Psi \rangle = -\frac{c}{4\pi} K \vec{A} \quad (24)$$

where K is the ‘London Kernel’ [3]. Both K and \vec{A} have wave vector dependence. which we omit here for simplicity. In the long wavelength limit this calculation yields [2, 3] $K = 1/\lambda_L^2$ where λ_L is the London penetration depth Eq. (11). Eq. (24) is the London equation Eq. (10).

In their original paper [2], BCS justified the ‘proof’ of the Meissner effect given above with the statement: “*The electrodynamic properties of our model are determined using a perturbation treatment in which the first order change in the wave function is used to calculate the current as a functional of the field. For such properties as the Meissner effect this approach is quite rigorous since we are interested in the limit as $\vec{A}(\vec{r})$ approaches zero.*” Many researchers in the field immediately questioned the validity of BCS’s proof of the Meissner effect. But, surprisingly, for the wrong reason. They focused on the fact that Eq. (24) used by BCS is not gauge invariant, and argued that the proof has to be valid in a gauge invariant way. After considerable mathematical elaborations, several workers independently proved that the non-gauge invariant BCS proof can be reformulated in a gauge-invariant way [42–44] and remains valid. This casted in stone the firm belief of the scientific community, ever since then to the present, that BCS theory has fully explained the Meissner effect.

However, the real weakness of the BCS justification for their proof of the Meissner effect is immediately apparent upon closer examination of their statement reproduced above. Their approach is not “*quite rigorous*”, and the fact that they are “*interested in the limit as $\vec{A}(\vec{r})$ approaches zero*” is irrelevant. The response of the system to a magnetic field, no matter how small it is, should be calculated with the system starting in its initial state, namely the normal state, not the unperturbed BCS state. The system cannot reach the BCS state while the magnetic field is present, no matter how small it is, simply because the BCS state requires macroscopic phase coherence and any infinitesimal magnetic field will destroy the phase coherence. Therefore, the BCS proof of the Meissner effect [2] proves nothing about the Meissner effect.

Finally, it is often said that the Meissner effect is the same as the Higgs mechanism in elementary particle physics and is explained by the fact that massless photons become massive when a metal goes superconducting [35, 45–48]. The argument is based on Ginzburg-Landau theory and also assumes that the system has a well-defined phase at the outset, hence doesn’t address the question of how the system reaches that state starting from the normal state. Therefore this also says nothing about how and why the Meissner effect occurs in materials.

The issue of reversibility, discussed in Sect. IV, is key to the Meissner effect. Under ideal conditions, the transition is thermodynamically reversible with no change in the entropy of the universe. This was well understood immediately after the Meissner effect was discovered [14–16, 22], and it is also implicit in the BCS description of the phenomenon. Therefore, any valid description of the Meissner effect needs to be able to describe a *reversible* process. This seems to have been forgotten in more recent times [38, 39, 49], but will be central in the considerations that follow.

VIII. PUZZLES WITH MOMENTUM IN THE MEISSNER EFFECT AND ITS REVERSE

In the above recount of arguments underlying the belief that the conventional theory of superconductivity explains the Meissner effect there was no mention of momentum. However, momentum is clearly involved in the Meissner effect and needs to be understood. The Meissner current that shields the external magnetic field carries mechanical momentum. The momentum density associated with electric current density $\vec{J}(\vec{r})$ is $\vec{P}(\vec{r}) = (m_e/e)\vec{J}(\vec{r})$, with m_e the bare electron mass and e the electron charge. For the cylinder of radius R and length ℓ considered in Sect. V, the total angular momentum carried by the supercurrent in an external field H is [50]

$$\vec{L}_e = -\frac{m_e c}{2e} \ell R^2 H \hat{z}. \quad (25)$$

This is a macroscopic angular momentum that can be (and has been) measured experimentally [51–53]. For a numerical example, for $R = 1\text{cm}$, $\ell = 5\text{cm}$ and $H = 200\text{G}$, $L_e = 2.84\text{mg} \cdot \text{mm}^2/\text{s}$. How this momentum originates and is conserved needs to be explained.

Fig. 3 shows in panel **a** a superconductor to which a magnetic field is applied, and the resulting state is shown in panel **b**. The Faraday electric field generated in the process, pointing clockwise as seen from the top, creates the surface current that prevents the field from penetrating. This is given quantitatively for free electrons by the London equation Eq. (10) reviewed in Sect VI. For electrons in a periodic potential the result is still Eq. (10) but with the electron bare mass in the London penetration depth Eq. (11) replaced by the band effective mass [50]. The current flows in clockwise direction and the electrons move in counterclockwise direction, as dictated by the Faraday field, carrying electronic angular momentum pointing up (parallel to the applied field). At the same time the Faraday electric field imparts clockwise momentum to the positively charged ions, and it is easily shown assuming charge neutrality that the body acquires clockwise momentum that exactly cancels the electronic angular momentum [50], as required. So this is all consistent and easy to understand.

Let us now consider the Meissner effect, shown in panels **c** and **d** of Fig. 3. The system is cooled into the

FIG. 3: Panels **a** and **b** show application of a magnetic field to a simply connected body that is already in the superconducting state. The Faraday electric field E_F points clockwise and gives rise to the clockwise current \mathbf{j} that prevents the magnetic field from penetrating, and to clockwise rotation of the body. Panels **c** and **d** show the Meissner effect. The Faraday electric field points in counterclockwise direction, yet the momentum acquired by the electrons and the body as a whole are the same as in panel **b**. The blue arrows on the electron and the ion on panels **b** and **d** indicate the direction of the force exerted by the Faraday field. .

superconducting state with magnetic field lines in the interior, which have to move out to reach the final state, so the Faraday electric field points now in opposite direction during the process, i.e. counterclockwise. The Faraday electric field pushes electrons to move clockwise and ions to move counterclockwise, as shown in Fig. 3 **d**. Yet the final state that is reached is identical to the one shown in panel **b**, i.e. electrons moving counterclockwise and the body rotating clockwise.

So it has to be explained: (1) How did the electrons in Fig. 3 **d** acquire momentum in direction opposite to that imparted by the Faraday electric field, and (2) how do the ions and hence the body as a whole acquire momentum in direction opposite to that imparted by the Faraday electric field? These questions need to be answered.

Similar puzzles occur in the inverse transition, from superconducting to normal, shown in Fig. 4. The Far-

FIG. 4: Inverse of the Meissner transition, right panel to left panel. System in a magnetic field goes from superconducting to normal. The Faraday field points clockwise, attempting to keep the clockwise current \mathbf{j} going and pushing the body to rotate in clockwise direction. In the final state (left panel) the current has stopped and the body rotates counterclockwise.

day field points clockwise, attempting to keep the current going, and pushes the body to rotate clockwise. Still, in the final state (left panel of Fig. 4) the body rotates counterclockwise, since it inherited the momentum of the electrons in the supercurrent, and the supercurrent has stopped. It has to be explained: (1) How did the supercurrent stop, against the Faraday field that pushed it to keep going, and (2) how does the body acquire momentum opposite to that imparted by the Faraday field on the ions.

It should be emphasized that any processes involving momentum transfers between electrons and the body as a whole need to be *reversible* processes, consistent with the fact that the Meissner effect is thermodynamically reversible under ideal conditions, as discussed in Sect. V. In this connection it is important to consider that it is experimentally found that for a material to undergo a complete Meissner effect it has to be extremely pure [31–33]. Any imperfections will lead to the diamagnetic moment under field cooling to be smaller than that under zero field cooling conditions, implying that some flux was not expelled but remained trapped in the interior of the material. This by itself strongly suggests that the mechanisms responsible for momentum transfer processes between electrons and ions under ideal conditions in the normal-superconductor transition in a magnetic field are not related to scattering mechanisms that give rise to finite resistance in the normal state such as impurities and imperfections that break the lattice periodicity, since those scattering processes are irreversible.

There has been one attempt to describe the superconductor to normal transition in a magnetic field within the conventional framework using time-dependent Ginzburg-Landau theory [36, 37] that took into account the momentum transfer between electrons and ions [54]. A term

in the current density in that formalism describes the current carried by normal electrons, stemming from the momentum transferred to the normal electron fluid when Cooper pairs carrying center of mass momentum unbind and the superfluid electron density decreases. The author states [54] that “*this momentum then decays with the transport relaxation time τ* ”. However, such decay would necessarily lead to Joule heat dissipation and hence irreversibility, therefore this approach cannot be correct. More generally, any approach that assumes that the momentum of the Cooper pair is transferred to normal quasiparticles when the system goes from superconducting to normal cannot be correct since in normal metallic transport decay of electric current is necessarily associated with Joule heat, thermodynamic irreversibility and even electromigration for high current densities. Rather, as correctly anticipated by Keesom early on [18], “*it is essential that the persistent currents have been annihilated before the material gets resistance*”.

IX. THE PUZZLES IN MORE DETAIL

We have seen in the last section that the momentum transfer between electrons and ions in the Meissner effect, as well as in the reverse process, the superconductor to normal transition, is opposite to what is dictated by Faraday’s law and its mechanism needs to be explained. In particular, in the superconductor to normal transition the initial momentum of the supercurrent, Eq. (25), needs to be transferred to the body as a whole without dissipation, and the initial kinetic energy of the supercurrent needs to go somewhere without dissipation. The puzzle of how the supercurrent stops without dissipation was first identified by Keesom, as discussed in Sect. IV. In fact, as we will show in this section, the total momentum transfer between electrons and ions that needs to occur and needs to be explained is many orders of magnitude larger than \vec{L}_e given by Eq. (25), and the total conversion of kinetic energy of the supercurrent to another energy (that is *not* Joule heat) that has to occur is many orders of magnitude larger than the initial kinetic energy of the supercurrent.

Let us consider the time evolution of the phase boundary between superconductor and normal phases in a cylindrical geometry for simplicity. The kinetics of the process for the superconductor to normal transition was first discussed by Pippard in a seminal paper in 1950 [55]. Pippard showed that what determines the rate of the transition can be simply calculated from electromagnetic considerations. Upon application of a magnetic field $H_c(1+p)$ slightly larger than H_c to the boundary, the magnetic field starts to penetrate at a speed such that the resulting Faraday electric field induces an opposite magnetic field in the growing normal region that reduces the value of the magnetic field at the boundary to exactly H_c . That speed is inversely proportional to the electrical conductivity of the normal region. Pippard

FIG. 5: Superconductor to normal transition in a cylinder as seen from the top. The magnetic field points out of the picture. On the left panel the phase boundary is at radius $r_0(t)$, and supercurrent circulates (approximately) in the region $r_0(t) - \lambda_L < r < r_0(t)$. On the right panel the phase boundary has moved to $r_0(t) - \lambda_L$, the supercurrent that was in the region $r_0(t) - \lambda_L < r < r_0(t)$ has stopped and now there is supercurrent in the region $r_0(t) - 2\lambda_L < r < r_0(t) - \lambda_L$. E_F is the Faraday electric field, and F_F denotes the force that E_F exerts on electrons, $F_F = eE_F$. The puzzle is, how did the red electrons on the right panel of the figure lose their kinetic energy and angular momentum in going from the superconducting region to the normal region as the phase boundary crossed them. And, how does the body acquire counterclockwise momentum when the Faraday field pushes the ions in clockwise direction.

deduced the approximate relation for the total transition time to be $\mathcal{T} = \pi\sigma R^2/p$ with R the cylinder radius. The total amount of Joule heat dissipated is inversely proportional to \mathcal{T} and the transition becomes reversible when it proceeds infinitely slowly, which will happen if $p \rightarrow 0$.

Let us analyze quantitatively the energy and momentum transfers in this process. We assume the phase boundary between normal and superconducting phases remains cylindrical. The supercurrent circulates within a distance approximately λ_L from the phase boundary of radius $r_0(t)$ where the applied magnetic field penetrates. The magnetic field is given by

$$B(r, t) = H_c e^{(r-r_0(t))/\lambda_L} \quad (26)$$

for $r \leq r_0(t)$, and the velocity of the electrons carrying the supercurrent is

$$v(r, t) = \frac{e\lambda_L}{m_e c} H_c e^{(r-r_0(t))/\lambda_L}. \quad (27)$$

With n_s superconducting electrons per unit volume the kinetic energy of the supercurrent is

$$K_e = 2\pi n_s \ell \int_0^{r_0} dr r \frac{1}{2} m_e v(r, t)^2 = \frac{H_c^2}{8\pi} \pi \ell r_0 \lambda_L. \quad (28)$$

At the beginning of the process, with $r_0 = R$, the initial kinetic energy of the supercurrent is

$$K_e = \frac{H_c^2}{8\pi} \pi \ell R \lambda_L = \frac{H_c^2}{8\pi} V \frac{\lambda_L}{R} \quad (29)$$

with $V = \pi R^2 \ell$ the volume of the superconductor.

When the phase boundary moves inward a distance dr_0 from r_0 , the superfluid electrons in the range $r_0 - dr_0 < r < r_0$ enter the normal region and stop their motion. More precisely, the center of mass momentum of the Cooper pair becomes zero as the pair unbinds. The change in kinetic energy when the superelectrons in the volume $2\pi r_0 dr_0 \ell$ go normal is

$$dK_e = \frac{H_c^2}{8\pi} (2\pi r_0 \ell) dr_0 \quad (30)$$

and the total change in kinetic energy as the phase boundary moves from $r_0 = R$ to $r_0 = 0$ is

$$K_e^{tot} = \int_0^R dK_e = \frac{H_c^2}{8\pi} V. \quad (31)$$

Thus,

$$K_e^{tot} = \frac{R}{\lambda_L} K_e \quad (32)$$

with K_e the initial energy of the supercurrent. The quantity Eq. (31) is the difference in free energies between normal and superconducting states, Eq. (6).

What Eqs. (31) and (32) say can be understood with the help of Fig. 5. As the phase boundary moves inward, a clockwise Faraday electric field E_F is generated that wants to preserve the supercurrent. The field exerts a clockwise force F_F on superelectrons in the interior of the

FIG. 6: Normal to superconductor transition in a cylinder as seen from the top. The magnetic field points out of the picture. On the left panel the phase boundary is at radius $r_0(t)$, and supercurrent circulates (approximately) in the region $r_0(t) - \lambda_L < r < r_0(t)$. On the right panel the phase boundary has moved to $r_0(t) + \lambda_L$, supercurrent in the region $r_0(t) < r < r_0(t) + \lambda_L$ was created. E_F is the Faraday electric field, that slows down electrons in the superconducting region as the phase boundary moves further outward. The puzzle is, how did the red electrons on the right panel of the figure acquire their kinetic energy and angular momentum in going from the normal to the superconducting region as the phase boundary crossed them. And, how does the body acquire clockwise momentum when the Faraday field pushes the ions in counterclockwise direction.

superconducting region that thereby acquire kinetic energy density $H_c^2/8\pi$ right when the phase boundary that is moving inward reaches them. At that point Cooper pairs dissociate, the electrons become normal with zero net momentum, and the kinetic energy of the supercurrent is used up in the dissociation of Cooper pairs, i.e. is the difference in free energies between normal and superconducting states given by Eq. (6). The total kinetic energy that is converted into free energy in the entire process, Eq. (32), is a factor R/λ_L larger than the initial kinetic energy of the supercurrent, e.g. 250,000 times larger for a typical example $R = 1\text{cm}$, $\lambda_L = 400\text{\AA}$. None of that kinetic energy gets dissipated as Joule heat.

Let us verify that the Faraday electric field is responsible for imparting the kinetic energy to the supercurrent. From Faraday's law and Eq. (26) for the magnetic field it follows that for $r \leq r_0$

$$E_F(r, t) = \frac{\lambda_L}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} H_c e^{(r-r_0(t))/\lambda_L} = \frac{\dot{r}_0}{c} H_c e^{(r-r_0(t))/\lambda_L} \quad (33)$$

and the change in velocity for superfluid carriers is given by

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} v(r, t) = e E_F(r, t) = \frac{e \lambda_L}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} H_c e^{(r-r_0(t))/\lambda_L} \quad (34)$$

which yields Eq. (27) upon time integration.

We can similarly understand what happens with the angular momentum transfer. The initial angular momentum of the supercurrent is L_e , Eq. (25). As the phase boundary moves inward the Faraday field imparts angular momentum to the supercarriers in the same direction.

The angular momentum of the supercurrent when the phase boundary is at radius r_0 is

$$L_e = 2\pi n_s \ell \int_0^{r_0} dr r (m_e v(r, t) r) = \frac{m_e c}{2\pi e} (\pi r_0^2 \ell) H_c. \quad (35)$$

When the phase boundary moves inward by dr_0 the supercurrent in that region stops. Its change in angular momentum is

$$dL_e = \frac{m_e c}{2\pi e} (\pi r_0^2 \ell) H_c \frac{dr_0}{\lambda_L} \quad (36)$$

so that the total change in angular momentum of electrons when the system goes from the superconducting to the normal state is

$$L_e^{tot} = \int_0^R dL_e = \frac{m_e c}{2\pi e} (\pi R^2 \ell) H_c \frac{R}{3\lambda_L} \quad (37)$$

hence

$$L_e^{tot} = \frac{R}{3\lambda_L} L_e. \quad (38)$$

For the example given above, $L_e^{tot} = 83,333 L_e$.

The angular momentum of electrons in the supercurrent is counterclockwise. So an amount of electronic angular momentum which is 5 orders of magnitude larger than the initial angular momentum of the supercurrent, almost all of it created by action of the Faraday electric field on the current carriers, disappears from the electronic system in the process of the transition from the

superconducting to the normal state. Of course it cannot disappear because angular momentum is conserved, hence must be transferred to the body as a whole. At the same time, the Faraday electric field imparts $83,332L_e$ clockwise angular momentum to the body as it acts on the ions in the superconducting region close to the phase boundary. The net result is that the body inherits exactly L_e of angular momentum from the electrons, the initial angular momentum of the supercurrent.

The mechanism by which the body acquired $83,332L_e$ clockwise angular momentum is clear, it is the momentum imparted to it by the Faraday electric field. The mechanism by which the electrons in the supercurrent when they entered the normal region stopped and transferred $83,333L_e$ counterclockwise angular momentum to the ions needs to be explained. Once again, it cannot entail normal electrons resulting from dissociation of Cooper pairs inheriting the center of mass momentum of the Cooper pairs and then transferring it to the body through scattering, because that would generate Joule heat. Joule heat is not allowed for two reasons: one is that it would make the process irreversible, and in addition it would violate conservation of energy since all the kinetic energy of the supercurrent was accounted for in the free energy difference between superconducting and normal states, as discussed above.

For the Meissner effect, where the processes just discussed run in reverse, the same puzzles arise. Fig. 6 shows a step in the normal to superconducting transition. The momentum and energy transfers between electrons and ions are in opposite directions to those of the previous case. Here one has to explain how electrons going from normal to superconducting acquire counterclockwise angular momentum when the Faraday field is pushing them clockwise, and how the ions acquire clockwise angular momentum when the Faraday field is pushing them counterclockwise. The total momentum and energy transfers between electrons and ions are the same in magnitude as in the previous case, i.e. many orders of magnitude larger than the final kinetic energy and angular momentum of the supercurrent.

X. THERMODYNAMIC FORCES VERSUS REAL FORCES, EMERGENCE VERSUS REDUCTIONISM

BCS theory has not addressed the questions discussed in the previous sections in the scientific literature. Possible answers to these questions within BCS theory have been gathered by this author from private communications with colleagues. Regarding energy, BCS will say that the theory satisfies energy conservation, and questions such as how does kinetic energy get converted into binding energy of Cooper pairs and vice versa do not need to be answered. In the Meissner effect, the system will find its way to its lowest energy state with the magnetic field excluded through ‘fluctuations’, regardless of the op-

posing Faraday field. Regarding momentum, BCS will say that there are “thermodynamic forces” that will give or take momentum to or from the electrons as they enter or leave the superconducting state in order to drive the system to its lower energy states, and that the ions will acquire compensating angular momentum because if they didn’t momentum conservation would be violated. And, that the processes may involve collisions, but if those collisions are elastic they would not generate Joule heat and not spoil reversibility. And, that in any event when phase boundaries move entropy is necessarily generated so the issue of reversibility is moot [49]. And, that superconductivity is an ‘emergent property’ [56, 57], hence seeking a reductionist answer that tries to identify microscopic mechanisms to explain these puzzles is fruitless.

Whether those answers are true or false is unknown. According to the general consensus [58], they are true and no further explanation of the issues discussed is needed [59]. In this author’s view, those answers are false [60]. ‘Thermodynamic forces’ ultimately arise from real forces, and it should be possible to identify the real forces at play in giving rise to the puzzling momentum transfer phenomena observed. Answers to those questions involving real forces have been proposed within the theory of hole superconductivity [61, 62].

It is generally said that there are only four forces in nature, namely gravitational, electromagnetic, weak and strong. Of those, clearly only the electromagnetic force can play a role. There is however also a fifth real force in nature, namely quantum pressure [63]. Quantum pressure is the fact that a quantum particle will lower its kinetic energy if its wavefunction expands. A particle in a box exerts a force against the walls because moving the walls outward will lower the quantum kinetic energy of the particle. Within the theory of hole superconductivity, answers to these questions result from action of the electromagnetic force and this quantum force. Whether those answers are true or false is unknown. According to the current general consensus they are false, but no specific reasons have been given for why they are false to this author’s knowledge.

XI. OVERVIEW OF PROPOSED REDUCTIONIST EXPLANATION

The key fact that can provide an explanation to all the puzzles described, that is predicted to occur [64] within the theory of hole superconductivity, is: *radial charge motion has to be involved*, as illustrated in Fig. 7. Qualitatively this is easy to understand. Electrons moving radially *outward*, under the influence of the Lorentz force

$$\vec{F}_L = \frac{e}{c} \vec{v} \times \vec{B} \quad (39)$$

will acquire azimuthal momentum such that the resulting current opposes the applied magnetic field, explaining the expulsion of magnetic field that is the Meissner effect

FIG. 7: Schematic depiction of radial motion of charge to explain the Meissner effect. Negative charge moving radially outward acquires counterclockwise azimuthal momentum through the Lorentz force, giving rise to the clockwise Meissner current that expels the magnetic field. Negative charge backflowing inward get clockwise azimuthal momentum through the Lorentz force and transfer that momentum to the ions, by a process explained later, thus ensuring momentum conservation.

[65]. Backflowing electrons flowing radially inward will acquire azimuthal momentum in opposite direction, and if they transfer this azimuthal momentum to the body as a whole it would not cancel the magnetic field expulsion but will cancel the mechanical momentum of the Meissner current, ensuring momentum conservation [66]. The driving force for radial outflow of electrons is quantum pressure of electrons going from the normal to the superconducting state, the driving force for backflow of normal electrons that transfer their azimuthal momentum to the lattice is the electric force resulting from the electric potential difference created by the radial outflow. The transfer of azimuthal momentum from backflowing electrons to the body occurs reversibly if the backflowing normal electrons have negative effective mass, hence are hole carriers [50], as explained in the next sections.

The key reason why scattering and dissipation is not involved in these processes is that the transfer of momentum is mediated by the electromagnetic field. That is what allows the kinetic energy of the supercurrent to remain in the electronic degrees of freedom, where it is used to pay the price of the condensation energy in rendering the superconducting electrons normal, and yet its momentum to be transferred to the ionic degrees of freedom.

In most physical interactions, momentum transfer is accompanied by energy transfer. An exception is when magnetic fields are involved. A charge moving in a magnetic field will change its momentum but not its kinetic energy: the magnetic Lorentz force $\propto \vec{v} \times \vec{B}$ is perpendicular to the particle's velocity \vec{v} . The momentum change of the particle is compensated by momentum

FIG. 8: Conceptual illustration of how momentum transfer between electrons and ions mediated by the electromagnetic field occurs in the Meissner effect. Magnetic field points out of the picture. We start with a charge-neutral system with one electron and one positive charge. In step 1, electron moving up acquires mechanical momentum P_e pointing left through the Lorentz force. Electric field E pointing up results from this charge motion, which gives rise to electromagnetic momentum P_{em} pointing right (Eq. (40)) that exactly cancels P_e . In step 2, positive charge moves up the same distance and acquires mechanical momentum to the right through the Lorentz force. The electromagnetic momentum disappears, and positive and negative charges acquired opposite momentum without any scattering processes involved.

FIG. 9: Same as Fig. 8 illustrating how the supercurrent stops and its momentum is transferred to positive charges in the superconductor to normal transition.

change of the electromagnetic field. The momentum density of the electromagnetic field is given by

$$\vec{\mathcal{P}}_{em}(\vec{r}) = \frac{1}{4\pi c} \vec{E} \times \vec{B} \quad (40)$$

with \vec{E} , \vec{B} electric and magnetic fields. In order for the electromagnetic momentum Eq. (40) to be azimuthal, and thus be able to mediate the azimuthal momentum transfer between electrons and ions, requires that the electric field \vec{E} in Eq. (40) is *radial*. To generate radial electric fields requires radial charge flow.

Let us understand conceptually how this transfer of momentum between electrons and ions mediated by the electromagnetic field can happen in the Meissner effect, with reference to Fig. 8. The up direction corresponds to radial outward motion of the superconductor-normal phase boundary. If the outward motion of the phase boundary is associated with outward motion of negative charge, the negative charge acquires momentum to the left (counterclockwise) through the Lorentz force, and this creates a transitory radially *outgoing* (upward in Fig. 8) electric field and hence a clockwise electromagnetic field momentum that compensates the counterclockwise mechanical momentum acquired by the outward-moving

electron due to the Lorentz force. In the subsequent step 2, positive charge moves up (radially outward) and the clockwise momentum of the electromagnetic field is transferred to the positive charge through the Lorentz force. The end result is negative and positive charges moving with the same momentum in opposite directions, as shown in the rightmost panel of Fig. 8. Similarly the processes that transfer the momentum of the supercurrent to positive charges in the superconductor to normal transition are shown in Fig. 9.

If the positive charges in Figs. 8 and 9 are ions, the processes explains how ions acquire the compensating momenta. However, of course ions in a solid cannot move radially outward nor inward. Instead, the positive charges in Figs. 8 and 9 are *holes*, or equivalently electrons with negative effective mass. The process of flux expulsion involves electrons becoming superconducting moving outward and at the same time normal holes moving outward to compensate for the charge imbalance and transfer momentum to the ions without scattering processes [50]. For the superconductor to normal transition the same processes occur, in reverse.

XII. CHARGE EXPULSION AND ALFVEN'S THEOREM

The fact that the Meissner effect, which involves outward motion of magnetic field lines, would be associated with outward motion of charge should not be surprising. That is precisely what classical plasmas would do. While the ultimate laws governing superconductivity operate in the quantum realm, superconductivity is a macroscopic phenomenon and Bohr's correspondence principle teaches us that there should be a smooth connection between classical and quantum realms. It is well known in the study of magnetohydrodynamics of conducting fluids that motion of magnetic field lines is closely associated with motion of charge [67]. This is codified precisely in Alfvén's theorem [68]: in a perfectly conducting fluid, magnetic field lines are frozen with the fluid and move together with the fluid. Of course this is a necessary consequence of Faraday's law. If the fluid is less than perfectly conducting there will be some relative motion of fluid and magnetic field lines, still, as P. H. Roberts points out [69], "*Alfvén's theorem is also helpful in attacking the problem of inferring unobservable fluid motions from observed magnetic field behavior*". For example, measurements of magnetic field variations near one of Jupiter's moons demonstrated the existence of an unobservable conducting fluid below its surface [70]. Isn't it reasonable to expect that the observed motion of magnetic field lines in the Meissner effect should allow us to infer '*unobservable fluid motions*' underlying it? [71]

Fig. 10 shows schematically the behavior of magnetic field lines resulting from jets of conducting fluid flowing from the center. They resemble the behavior of magnetic field lines in the Meissner effect, Fig. 1. In a classical

FIG. 10: The right half of this figure is Fig. 2.8 of Ref. [67], "An Introduction to Magnetohydrodynamics", with caption "*An example of Alfvén's theorem: flow through a magnetic field causes the field lines to bow out*", illustrating the bending of magnetic field lines by a jet of conducting fluid. The left half of the figure was copied from the right side and flipped horizontally.

plasma such fluid flow would not occur, since it would give rise to a void at the center. It requires outward flow of a fluid that carries neither net charge nor net mass. In a metal going superconducting it can occur if what flows out is negative electrons and positive holes, since holes flowing out is associated with real mass (electron mass) flowing in.

Let us consider again the treatment of London electrodynamics of Sect. VI, where some terms were neglected. Rather than Eq. (7), the more accurate equation is

$$\frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} = \frac{e}{m_e} \vec{E} + \frac{e}{m_e c} \vec{v} \times \vec{B} \quad (41)$$

The left-hand side of Eq. (41) is the total (convective) time derivative, which is related to the local (partial) time derivative by

$$\frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} = \frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} + (\vec{v} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{v} = \frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \left(\frac{\vec{v}^2}{2} \right) - \vec{v} \times (\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{v}) \quad (42)$$

Defining the 'generalized vorticity'

$$\vec{w} = \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{v} + \frac{e}{m_e c} \vec{B}, \quad (43)$$

taking the curl of Eq. (41) and using Eq. (42) and Faraday's law $\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -(1/c) \partial \vec{B} / \partial t$ leads to the following equation of motion for \vec{w} [28]:

$$\frac{\partial \vec{w}}{\partial t} = \vec{\nabla} \times (\vec{v} \times \vec{w}). \quad (44)$$

Note that \vec{w} is essentially the curl of the canonical momentum $\vec{p} = m_e \vec{v} + (e/c) \vec{A}$, with \vec{A} the magnetic vector potential. In the Meissner process we have at time $t = 0$: $\vec{w}(\vec{r}, t = 0) = e/(m_e c) \vec{B}(t = 0) \equiv \vec{w}_0 \neq 0$ independent of position \vec{r} . We set $\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{v} = 0$ because in the normal state there is no net macroscopic charge flow.

Hence the canonical momentum \vec{p} is nonzero throughout the interior of the superconductor in the initial state. In the superconducting state, the superfluid velocity \vec{v} obeys the London equation $\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{v} = -e/(m_e c) \vec{B}$. Therefore, $\vec{w}(\vec{r}, t = \infty) = 0$ everywhere in the superconducting body. Equivalently, the canonical momentum $\vec{p} = 0$ throughout the interior of the (simply connected) superconductor. In a cylindrical geometry, assuming azimuthal symmetry as well as translational symmetry along the cylinder axis (z) direction (infinitely long cylinder) $\vec{w}(\vec{r}, t) = w(r, t) \hat{z}$ and Eq. (44) takes the form

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r w v_r) \quad (45)$$

with r the radius in cylindrical coordinates. Eq. (45) implies that w can only change if there is radial flow of charge ($v_r \neq 0$). Moreover, for w to evolve towards its final value 0 requires $v_r > 0$, i.e. a radial outflow of electrons.

XIII. MOMENTUM TRANSFERS BY RADIAL MOTION

How much charge needs to flow radially out and how far to explain the Meissner effect? The answer is simple [72]. The velocity of electrons in the Meissner current for magnetic field B at the phase boundary is

$$v_s = -\frac{e \lambda_L}{m_e c} H_c. \quad (46)$$

While Eq. (27) gave the more detailed radial dependence of the Meissner velocity, it is equivalent to saying that all electrons within distance λ_L of the surface or of the phase boundary between superconducting and normal phases are moving with velocity Eq. (46). If in the process of joining the condensate normal electrons form Cooper pairs and move radially outward, as shown schematically in Fig. 11, they will acquire through the Lorentz force Eq. (39) azimuthal velocity v_θ given by

$$\frac{dv_\theta}{dt} = \frac{e}{m_e c} \frac{dr}{dt} B \quad (47)$$

hence

$$\Delta v_\theta = \frac{e}{m_e c} \Delta r B \quad (48)$$

Therefore, if initially the electron had zero azimuthal velocity on average, by moving radially outward a distance $\Delta r = \lambda_L$ it will acquire the azimuthal momentum required by the Meissner velocity Eq. (46):

$$\Delta p = \frac{e \lambda_L}{c} H_c. \quad (49)$$

The outward motion needs to be sufficiently fast so that we can ignore the azimuthal momentum in the opposite

FIG. 11: Schematic depiction of momentum transfers in the Meissner effect. Green electron moving radially outward a distance λ_L acquires through the Lorentz force counter-clockwise azimuthal momentum with velocity equal to the azimuthal velocity of electrons in the Meissner current, Eq. (46). Backflowing brown electron acquires the same azimuthal momentum in clockwise direction through the Lorentz force and transfers it to the ions.

direction imparted by the Faraday electric field during this process.

To compensate for this change in azimuthal momentum, as well as to preserve charge homogeneity, there needs to be a backflow of normal electrons that acquire the same azimuthal momentum in clockwise direction through the Lorentz force, and transfer that momentum to the body as a whole, as also shown schematically in Fig. 11.

In summary, the processes shown in Fig. 11 explain qualitatively how the puzzling momentum transfers happen. Each electron when transiting from the normal to the superconducting state sprints radially outward a distance λ_L and in the process acquires the azimuthal momentum needed to contribute its share to the Meissner current. And for each such outflow there is a backflowing electron that acquires the same azimuthal momentum in the opposite direction and transfers it to the body.

How this happens in detail is discussed in the following sections.

XIV. MOMENTUM TRANSFER TO THE IONS

We first discuss how backflowing normal electrons transfer azimuthal momentum to the body without collisions. The relevant forces are shown in Fig. 12. The Faraday electric force is

$$F_E = e E_F = e \frac{\dot{r}_0}{c} H_c \quad (50)$$

and it is identical to the magnetic Lorentz force

$$F_B = e \frac{\dot{r}_0}{c} H_c \quad (51)$$

FIG. 12: How normal electrons backflowing into the phase boundary with speed \dot{r}_0 transfer azimuthal momentum to the lattice without scattering processes in the Meissner effect. F_E is the electric force due to the Faraday field E_F , F_B is the magnetic Lorentz force for speed of motion \dot{r}_0 , and $F_{latt} = F_E + F_B = 2F_E = 2F_B$ is the force exerted by the lattice on the electron. $F_{on-latt} = F_{latt}$ is the reaction force of the electron on the body.

imparted to normal electrons backflowing with speed \dot{r}_0 . Both forces point clockwise. Just like for electrons in a Hall bar with positive Hall coefficient, the electromagnetic forces are balanced by the force exerted by the lattice on the electron, F_{latt} , provided the electron has negative effective mass [23, 50]:

$$F_{latt} = 2e \frac{\dot{r}_0}{c} H_c = F_{on-latt}. \quad (52)$$

By Newton's third law, the electrons exert equal and opposite force on the lattice, i.e. in clockwise direction, $F_{on-latt}$. The momentum that is transferred to the lattice by the normal electron backflowing a radial distance λ_L in time Δt , with $\dot{r}_0 = \lambda_L / \Delta t$ is then

$$\Delta p_{on-latt} = F_{on-latt} \Delta t = 2e \frac{\dot{r}_0}{c} H_c \Delta t = 2 \frac{e \lambda_L}{c} H_c. \quad (53)$$

In addition the Faraday electric field, by exerting force on the positive ions transfers half of that momentum in counterclockwise direction, hence the net transfer of momentum to the body is

$$\Delta p_{on-latt}^{net} = \frac{e \lambda_L}{c} H_c. \quad (54)$$

identical to the momentum in counterclockwise direction acquired by the outflowing electrons, Eq. (49).

This requires that backflowing electrons have negative effective mass, as explained in detail in the references [23, 50?].

XV. MOMENTUM TRANSFER TO THE ELECTRONS

Assume that in the process of forming Cooper pairs and becoming superconducting, electrons expand their

FIG. 13: Normal electrons with orbits of microscopic radius expand their orbits to radius $2\lambda_L$ as they enter the superconducting region. Through the action of the Lorentz force on the expanding orbit they acquire the azimuthal velocity of the Meissner current Eq. (46)

orbits from a microscopic radius of order k_F^{-1} , with k_F the Fermi wavevector, to mesoscopic radius $2\lambda_L$. We will discuss in the next section why this is reasonable. If that happens, when electrons at the phase boundary expand their orbits they will expand into the normal region, as shown in Fig. 13. Through the action of the Lorentz force on the expanding orbit, the azimuthal velocity that the electron acquires is precisely the speed of the Meissner current, Eq. (46). This is seen as follows: the equation of motion as the electron moves radially outward is

$$m_e \frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} = \frac{e}{c} \vec{v} \times \vec{B} + \vec{F}_r \quad (55)$$

where the first term is the magnetic Lorentz force and we have included a radial force arising from ‘‘quantum pressure’’ that drives the orbit expansion. From Eq. (55) we infer

$$\vec{r} \times \frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} = \frac{e}{m_e c} \vec{r} \times (\vec{v} \times \vec{B}) \quad (56)$$

where \vec{r} is in the plane perpendicular to the axis of the cylinder. Hence $\vec{r} \cdot \vec{B} = 0$ and $\vec{r} \times (\vec{v} \times \vec{B}) = -(\vec{r} \cdot \vec{v}) \vec{B}$, and

$$\frac{d}{dt} (\vec{r} \times \vec{v}) = -\frac{e}{m_e c} (\vec{r} \cdot \vec{v}) \vec{B} = -\frac{e}{2m_e c} \left(\frac{d}{dt} r^2 \right) \vec{B} \quad (57)$$

so that $\vec{r} \times \vec{v} = -(e/2m_e c) r^2 \vec{B}$, and the acquired azimuthal velocity in moving out a distance r is

$$v_\phi = -\frac{e}{2m_e c} r B \quad (58)$$

Thus, the electron acquires azimuthal speed $v_s = -e\lambda_L / (m_e c) B$ in expanding its orbit to radius $r = 2\lambda_L$. In the region right outside the phase boundary the expanded orbits overlap the microscopic orbits of normal electrons, as seen in Fig. 14, and the extra negative charge induces the inward ‘backflow’ of normal electrons.

The above provides a dynamical explanation for how electrons acquire the azimuthal velocity of the Meissner current as they enter the superconducting state. In the next section we present several arguments in favor of this hypothesis.

FIG. 14: Superconducting electrons reside in overlapping mesoscopic orbits of radius $2\lambda_L$. In the normal region, electrons reside in non-overlapping microscopic orbits of radius k_F^{-1} . The negative charge from the expanded orbits extends into the normal region and induces the ‘backflow’ of normal electrons shown in Figs. 11 and 12.

XVI. MESOSCOPIC ORBITS

The Larmor diamagnetic susceptibility for carriers of density n in orbits of radius r is [74]

$$\chi_{Larmor}(r) = -\frac{ne^2}{4m_e c^2} r^2 \quad (59)$$

It is remarkable that the normal state Landau diamagnetism of metals is described by this expression for normal state orbits of microscopic radius k_F^{-1} :

$$\chi_{Landau} = -\frac{1}{3} \mu_B^2 g(\epsilon_F) = -\frac{ne^2}{4m_e c^2} k_F^{-2} = \chi_{Larmor}(k_F^{-1}) \quad (60)$$

with k_F the Fermi wavevector, $g(\epsilon_F) = 3n/2\epsilon_F$ the free electron density of states, and $\mu_B = e\hbar/2m_e c$ the Bohr magneton. It is also remarkable that the perfect diamagnetism of the superconducting state is described by the Larmor formula Eq. (59) for orbits of mesoscopic radius $2\lambda_L$:

$$\chi_{London} = -\frac{1}{4\pi} = -\frac{ne^2}{4m_e c^2} (2\lambda_L)^2 = \chi_{Larmor}(2\lambda_L) \quad (61)$$

with the London penetration depth λ_L given by the usual form Eq. (11) and $n_s = n$ the superfluid density. This indicates that (i) the transition to superconductivity can be understood as involving an *expansion* of electronic orbits from radius k_F^{-1} to radius $2\lambda_L$, and (ii) that the superconducting ground state can be understood as being composed of all electrons ($n_s = n$) residing in orbits of radius $2\lambda_L$ [73].

This is further supported by the observation that the angular momentum carried by the electrons in the Meissner current with velocity v_s in a cylinder of radius $R \gg$

FIG. 15: The Meissner current resulting from carriers within a shell of thickness λ_L from the surface circulating with speed v_s (left panel) can be regarded as arising from individual electrons orbiting with the same speed in overlapping orbits of radius $2\lambda_L$, as shown by Eq. (62).

FIG. 16: Cylindrical shell cooled into the superconducting state in the presence of a magnetic field as seen from the top. Currents flow along the outer and inner surfaces in opposite directions. This is a natural consequence of the orbits expanding in a magnetic field and acquiring counterclockwise velocity through the Lorentz force.

λ_L and height ℓ can be written in the two equivalent forms:

$$\begin{aligned} L_{Meissner} &= n_s(2\pi R\lambda_L\ell) \times (m_e v_s R) \\ &= n_s(\pi R^2\ell) \times (m_e v_s(2\lambda_L)) \end{aligned} \quad (62)$$

The first form is the conventional description of electrons flowing in a surface layer of thickness λ_L , hence cross-sectional area $2\pi R\lambda_L$, each moving in a circle of radius R . The second form describes all electrons in the bulk, hence cross-sectional area πR^2 , each moving in a mesoscopic orbit of radius $2\lambda_L$. This is shown schematically in Fig. 15.

This concept is also helpful for understanding what happens when a cylindrical shell is cooled in a magnetic field, as shown in Fig. 16. The magnetic flux in the empty region inside the shell remains essentially unchanged, up to at most a fraction of a flux quantum which we ignore. During the process, a clockwise Faraday electric field exists opposing the expulsion of flux from the shell. The field is expelled from the shell region, which

FIG. 17: Rotating cylindrical shell that is cooled into the superconducting state while rotating. In the normal state, electrons and ions rotate with the same tangential speed ωr . A uniform magnetic field develops in the interior. This means that electrons near the outer surface need to slow down and electrons near the inner surface need to speed up relative to their motions in the normal state.

requires that supercurrents flow in opposite directions along the outer and inner surfaces of the shell. Within the ‘emergence’ viewpoint, there is no explanation for how electrons acquire their momentum in opposite directions in the outer and inner surfaces, it follows from the equations and the fact that the system ends up in the lowest energy state. Instead, within our ‘reductionist’ point of view, the fact that electrons acquire opposite velocities in the outer and inner surfaces is a natural consequence of the expansion of microscopic orbits to radius $2\lambda_L$, as shown in Fig. 16.

XVII. ROTATING SUPERCONDUCTORS

Another situation related to the Meissner effect occurs when a normal metal that is rotating is cooled into the superconducting state, in the absence of applied field. This is called the London moment. Fig. 17 shows what happens for a rotating cylindrical shell [75]. A uniform magnetic field develops in the interior of the shell, which implies that currents are generated that circulate in opposite directions near the outer and inner shell surfaces. When the system is rotating in the normal state, electrons and ions move at the same tangential speed given by ωr , with ω the angular velocity and r the radial position of the ion or electron. For the magnetic field to develop in the interior of the shell, in the transition to superconductivity the electrons near the outer surface need to slow down and those the inner surface need to speed up, as shown in Fig. 17

This behavior is easy to understand with $2\lambda_L$ orbits [76], as shown in Fig. 18. In the normal state we can think of the electron at radius r as a point particle, with moment of inertia $m_e r^2$ and angular momentum $l_e = m_e r^2 \omega$. When its orbit expands to radius $2\lambda_L$ its angular momentum cannot change. That means that it has to start rotating in clockwise direction with angular velocity ω in the rest frame of the rotating cylinder, as indicated

FIG. 18: Explanation of why electrons speed up and slow down near the inner and upper surfaces of the shell of Fig. 17. Electrons enlarge their orbits from a microscopic radius to radius $2\lambda_L$, with their total angular momentum unchanged. This implies that they rotate clockwise with angular velocity ω in the rotating frame, as shown by the red arrow on the right panel.

by the red arrow in Fig. 18, since

$$l_e = m_e r^2 \omega = m_e (r^2 + (2\lambda_L)^2) \omega - m_e (2\lambda_L)^2 \omega. \quad (63)$$

Superposition of the resulting rotating orbits, just as shown in Fig. 16 right panel, gives rise to slowdown near the outer surface and speedup near the inner surface, as required by the velocity patterns shown in Fig. 17 right panel.

Quantitatively this is understood as follows. The London equation

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{v}_s = -\frac{e}{m_e c} \vec{B} \quad (64)$$

is assumed to be valid, with \vec{v}_s the velocity of electrons in the non-rotating frame. Deep in the interior of the shell electrons rotate at the same speed as ions, with velocity $\vec{v}_s = \vec{\omega} \times \vec{r}$ at radius r . Since $\vec{\nabla} \times (\omega \times \vec{r}) = 2\vec{\omega}$, it follows that the magnetic field is

$$\vec{B}_0 = -\frac{2m_e c}{e} \vec{\omega}. \quad (65)$$

Now at the outer surface, the relative velocity between electrons and the body gives rise to the interior field, hence

$$\vec{\nabla} \times (\vec{v}_s - \vec{v}_0) = -\frac{e}{m_e c} \vec{B}_0 \quad (66)$$

from which it follows in the usual way

$$v_s - v_0 = -\frac{e\lambda_L}{m_e c} B_0 \quad (67)$$

hence

$$v_s - v_0 = -2\lambda_L \omega. \quad (68)$$

Eq. (68) says that the slowdown of electrons at the outer surface is identical to what would result if electrons expanded their orbits to radius $2\lambda_L$ and in the process acquired clockwise angular velocity ω , as shown in Fig. 18.

FIG. 19: Streamlines for electrons entering and leaving the superconducting region of a cylindrical wire. The circles indicate magnetic field lines.

The same physics leads to, for electrons near the inner surface of the shell

$$v_s - v_0 = +2\lambda_L\omega. \quad (69)$$

so electrons speed up relative to the ions to cancel the magnetic field in the empty region inside the shell.

Within an “emergent” viewpoint, these results are a consequence the equations, and the question of what is the dynamics leading electrons to slow down and speed up near the surfaces is not asked. Instead, within a “reductionist” viewpoint one would like to understand the dynamic processes involved. Expansion of electronic orbits to radius $2\lambda_L$ provide an answer that is understandable and quantitatively correct, as discussed above.

XVIII. SUPERCONDUCTING WIRE

A superconducting wire connected to normal metal leads presents another interesting situation to contrast emergent and reductionist understandings of the situation. Fig. 19 show the streamlines and magnetic field lines for this case. They are simply obtained from solving London’s equation Eq. (10) together with Ampere’s law and the boundary conditions appropriate to this situation [28]. The streamlines show a discontinuous slope at the boundaries between normal and superconducting regions. Within a ‘reductionist’ approach one may wonder, what are the forces that make carriers discontinuously change their direction when they cross the phase boundary? Instead, within an ‘emergence’ approach, there would be no reason to ask that question. That is what the London equation predicts, which in turn is predicted by BCS theory, that dictates that the system knows how to find its way to its lowest energy state, even in a non-static steady state situation.

Consider the cylindrical wire along the z direction, with $-b < z < b$ denoting the superconducting region, and current density J flowing in the $-z$ direction, as shown in in Fig. 19 [77]. At the N-S boundary $z = -b$, the current streamlines acquire *discontinuously* motion in the *outward* radial direction, as seen in Fig. 19. The same is true at the S-N boundary $z = +b$. From the equations and boundary conditions we find that the radial velocity $v_r(r, z)$ acquired at the phase boundary is,

FIG. 20: In order for carriers to acquire the speed Eq. (70) in the outward radial direction as they enter or leave the superconducting region, they have to undergo a sudden motion in the $-z$ direction a distance λ_L (red arrows). The magnetic field provides the radial impulse through the Lorentz force, it points into (out of) the paper in the top (bottom) half of the figure, as indicated by the crosses and circles.

in terms of the azimuthal magnetic field $B_\theta(r, z)$

$$v_r(r, -b) = -\frac{e\lambda_L}{m_e c} B_\theta(r, -b) = \frac{r}{2\lambda_L} v_n \quad (70)$$

where $v_n = J/(ne)$ is the carrier velocity in the normal region in direction parallel to the wire, where n is the density of carriers. The magnetic field is given by

$$B_\theta(r, -b) = \frac{2\pi}{c} Jr \quad (71)$$

linearly proportional to r , since the current density is uniformly distributed across the wire in the normal region. Eq. (70) implies that as carriers enter the superconducting region they suddenly acquire a very large radial impulse (for $r \gg \lambda_L$) in direction parallel to the phase boundary. Presumably this occurs over a very short time scale, which implies that an enormous force in the radial direction is acting on the charge carriers as they enter the superconducting region. Eq. (70) indicates that it is the magnetic field B_θ that imparts the impulse to the carriers in the radial direction as they become superconducting: the impulse is zero if $B_\theta = 0$ and it is directly proportional to the local value of B_θ for a given r , with the same proportionality constant independent of r . And the impulse points in direction perpendicular to \vec{B} . It is natural to conclude that the impulse results from the magnetic Lorentz force acting on carriers entering the superconducting region:

$$\vec{F}_L = \frac{e}{c} \vec{v} \times \vec{B}. \quad (72)$$

In order for the electron to get an impulse in the radial direction given that \vec{B} is in the azimuthal direction, \vec{v} in Eq. (72) has to point in the $-\hat{z}$ direction, as shown in Fig. 20.

The carriers flowing from the normal into the superconducting region acquire the velocity v_r instantly as they cross the phase boundary. Let us assume that the instant they cross the phase boundary $z = -b$ they recoil backward (in the $-z$ direction) a distance $\Delta\ell$ in a very short time interval Δt , so in Eq. (72) $v = \Delta\ell/\Delta t$. In order to

FIG. 21: The processes of orbit expansion and contraction as carriers enter and leave the superconducting region explain the sudden impulses in the $-z$ direction and resulting radial impulses acquired by the carriers at the boundaries shown in Fig. 20.

acquire the speed in the r direction given by Eq. (70) under the action of the Lorentz force Eq. (72) it is necessary that $\Delta\ell = \lambda_L$, so that $F_L\Delta t = (e/c)\Delta\ell B = m_e v_r$. Similarly, when charges leave the condensate at $z = +b$, they also have to acquire a sudden impulse in the *outward* radial direction of the same magnitude as when they entered (see streamlines in Fig. 19 near $z = b$). Again this would result if they move backward (in the $-z$ direction) a distance $\Delta\ell = \lambda_L$.

We can understand this behavior with the same concept of mesoscopic orbits discussed earlier, illustrated in Fig. 21. When normal carriers enter the superconducting region their orbits expand from microscopic radius to radius $2\lambda_L$. Just like we discussed earlier in connection with the momentum transfers in the Meissner effect, the same momentum is acquired through the Lorentz force if the motion is linear over a distance λ_L or if the orbit expands to radius $2\lambda_L$. In the presence of a magnetic field, carriers acquire angular velocity that gives rise to the tangential velocity given by Eq. (70). Conversely, when pairs leave the condensate their orbits contract and their tangential velocity goes to zero, hence the motion for $z > b$ is parallel to the z direction.

XIX. THEORY OF HOLE SUPERCONDUCTIVITY

The ‘reductionist’ explanations of momentum transfers associated with the Meissner effect and related phenomena discussed in the earlier sections were developed within the alternative theory of hole superconductivity [61, 62]. We summarize here the key elements of the theory.

(1) The theory predicted from the outset [78] that superconductivity requires hole carriers.

(2) There is a fundamental asymmetry between carriers near the bottom and near the top of electronic energy bands in solids [79, 80]. This gives rise to a term in the Coulomb interaction between electrons that breaks electron-hole symmetry that becomes increasingly attractive as the Fermi level approaches the top of the band, that gives rise to pairing and superconductivity [81, 82].

(3) The attractive interaction lowers the kinetic energy

of pairs [83], so superconductivity is driven by lowering of kinetic energy rather than potential energy as in BCS.

(4) Kinetic energy lowering drives the orbit expansion discussed earlier [84]. The quantum kinetic energy of an electronic wavefunction of radius r is $\hbar^2/(m_e r^2)$ and it decreases as r increases.

(5) The effective mass of normal carriers at the Fermi energy is negative because the Fermi level is close to the top of the band. As discussed earlier this is essential to explain the transfer of momentum to ions without dissipation.

(6) In the condensate, carriers occupy overlapping mesoscopic orbits of radius $2\lambda_L$, and the two members of a Cooper pair orbit in opposite direction, with zero-point velocity [73]

$$v_\sigma^0 = \frac{\hbar}{4m_e\lambda_L}. \quad (73)$$

Hence their orbital angular momentum is $\hbar/2$. The orbiting direction is determined by the spin-orbit interaction.

(7) Phase coherence is a consequence of the fact that the $2\lambda_L$ orbits are strongly overlapping.

(8) In the presence of a magnetic field H , the velocity of one of the members of the Cooper pair increases by $e\lambda_L H/(m_e c)$, the other decreases by the same amount, and superconductivity breaks down when the slower velocity goes to zero, which determines the critical field as

$$H_{crit} = \frac{\hbar c}{4e\lambda_L^2} \quad (74)$$

This is essentially the same as the lower critical field value H_{c1} in BCS theory [3].

(9) The charge distribution in the ground state of superconductors is macroscopically inhomogeneous, with more negative charge near the surface and more positive charge in the interior [85, 86]. Even though this costs potential energy, it minimizes the total energy, i.e. potential plus kinetic. The excess charge density near the surface is [87]

$$\rho_- = en_s \frac{v_\sigma^0}{c} \quad (75)$$

and associated with it there is an electric field in the interior of superconductors pointing radially outward, that reaches maximum value

$$E_m = \frac{\hbar c}{4e\lambda_L^2} = H_{crit} \quad (76)$$

within a London penetration depth of the surface of the superconductor.

(10) Electrodynamics of superconductors is somewhat different from what is described by London theory [86]. While London’s equation in the form Eq. (14) still holds, the gauge obeyed by the vector potential \vec{A} in that equation is the Lorenz gauge rather than the Coulomb gauge.

Electrodynamic equations are relativistically covariant, given in terms of 4-vectors by

$$J - J_0 = -\frac{c}{4\pi\lambda_L^2}(A - A_0) \quad (77)$$

with $J = (\vec{J}(\vec{r}, t), ic\rho(\vec{r}, t))$, $A = (\vec{A}(\vec{r}, t), i\phi(\vec{r}, t))$, $J_0 = (0, ic\rho_0)$, $A_0 = (\vec{A}(0, i\phi_0(\vec{r}, t)))$, with ϕ the electric potential and

$$\phi_0(\vec{r}) = \int_V d^3r' \frac{\rho_0}{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|}. \quad (78)$$

In particular, this implies that applied electrostatic fields are screened over a distance given by the London penetration depth rather than the much shorter Thomas Fermi length. The value of ρ_0 is determined by the value of the charge density near the surface of the sample Eq. (75) and charge neutrality.

(11) There is a macroscopic spin current in the ground state of superconductors flowing within a London penetration depth of the surface [73], which is a macroscopic zero point motion of the superfluid. It results from the expansion of orbits to radius $2\lambda_L$ and the spin-orbit interaction with the background positive charge distribution. We have called this the ‘Spin Meissner effect’ [73]. The electrodynamic equations for the charge and spin sectors are given in Ref. [87].

(12) The pairing interaction and resulting critical temperature T_c is largest for systems with holes conducting through closely spaced negatively charged anions [88]. The mass of the ions is not important to determine the value of T_c , even though a small isotope effect can arise from small variations in the value of the ionic mass.

These and many more details of the theory are given in the references in [61].

XX. PRECEDENTS AND OTHER VIEWS OF THE MEISSNER EFFECT

Various elements of the ‘reductionist’ view of the Meissner effect discussed in this paper, that are not part of the ‘emergent’ BCS view, were in fact proposed in early work before the theory of hole superconductivity was developed. We list them here.

(1) H. G. Smith [89, 90]. proposed in 1935 that the perfect diamagnetism of superconductors results from electronic orbits that are very large compared with atomic dimensions. More specifically, Slater proposed in 1937 [91] that “to produce superconductivity the orbits must be of the order of magnitude of 137 atomic diameters”. This is closely related to the $2\lambda_L$ orbits discussed earlier. With $137 = \hbar c/e^2$, atomic diameter $2a_0$ with a_0 the Bohr radius, and atomic density $1/(2a_0)^3$, the radius of Slater’s orbits is $2\lambda_L \times \sqrt{\pi}/2$, with λ_L given by Eq. (11).

(2) K. M. Koch proposed in 1940-45 [92-94] as an explanation of the Meissner effect that electrons flowing outward in the transition to superconductivity, due to a

thermoelectric effect or other reasons, would be deflected by the Lorentz force in the azimuthal direction so as to suppress the initial field, just as discussed here.

(3) W. H. Cherry proposed in 1960 [95] that in the transition to superconductivity there would be nucleation and growth processes where outward diffusion of electrons would give rise under the action of the Lorentz force to currents that would weaken the magnetic field in the interior, and electrons backflowing to compensate for the charge imbalance would transfer the thrusts they receive from the magnetic field to the lattice. This is closely related to the processes of radial outflow and backflow discussed here within the ‘reductionist view’.

(4) Several workers before BCS proposed models with ‘spontaneous currents’, or ‘circulating currents’ in the ground state of superconductors. Among them Bloch [96], Frenkel [97], Landau [98], Smith [89, 90], Born, Cheng [99] and Heisenberg [100]. The currents were assumed to be charge currents, with different orientations in different domains so that no net magnetic field would be generated. This is related to the spin currents in the ground state of superconductors resulting from $2\lambda_L$ orbits mentioned earlier [73].

(5) F. London remarked in the Introduction to his 1950 book [28] “According to quantum theory the most stable state of any system is not a state of static equilibrium in the configuration of lowest potential energy. It is rather a kind of kinetic equilibrium for the so-called zero point motion, which may roughly be characterized as defined by the minimum average total (potential + kinetic) energy”. And he added “It is not necessarily a configuration close to the minimum of the potential energy (lattice order) which is the most advantageous one for the energy balance, since by virtue of the uncertainty relation the kinetic energy also comes into play. If the resultant forces are sufficiently weak and act between sufficiently light particles, then the structure possessing the smallest total energy would be characterized by a good economy of the kinetic energy ... It would be the outcome of a quantum mechanism of macroscopic scale.”. These concepts are not part of BCS theory, and foreshadowed the predictions of the theory of hole superconductivity that the ground state charge distribution in superconductors is macroscopically inhomogeneous, costing potential energy, and the energy lowering is due to quantum kinetic energy.

None of the physics discussed in (1)-(5) above is part of the conventional BCS ‘emergent viewpoint’ of the Meissner effect, and all of it is related to the ‘reductionist viewpoint’ discussed here.

Finally, we mention here some other viewpoints on the Meissner effect that have been proposed. We don’t believe they are right.

(1) Essen and Fiolhais [101] proposed in 2012 that magnetic flux expulsion from a sample cooled to superconductivity can be understood as an approach to the magnetostatic energy minimum, with quantum mechanics playing no role, and without the necessity of a con-

FIG. 22: Cooling of a simply connected superconductor with a small cavity in its interior in a small uniform magnetic field (blue lines). The state of lowest energy has currents (red curves) circulating near the surface only and the magnetic field is totally expelled from the interior including the cavity.

FIG. 23: A possible outcome of cooling a simply connected superconductor with a small cavity in its interior in a magnetic field. The state shown on the right panel has magnetic flux trapped and higher energy than the state shown in Fig. 22 right panel.

densation energy for the superconducting state.

(2) Krüger [102] in 2017 proposed that the Meissner effect results from ‘quantum mechanical constraining forces’ that in the presence of a magnetic field produce Cooper pairs of non-vanishing total momentum in nearly half-filled narrow energy bands.

(3) Nikulov [103, 104] argued in 2022 that in the superconductor to normal transition the supercurrent stops through normal scattering processes generating Joule heat, and that this implies that the Meissner effect is a phenomenon where the second law of thermodynamics is violated.

(4) Koizumi [105] proposed in 2024 that there are several additional important forces besides the Lorentz force in superconductors, in particular there is a ‘force’ for producing topologically protected loop currents that explains the Meissner effect.

(5) Kozhevnikov [106] proposed in (2021) that “a novel semi-classical micro-whirls model” explains the Meissner effect. Whether or not this has any relation with the $2\lambda_L$ orbits discussed here was not discussed in [106].

XXI. A TEST CASE

Here we discuss a test that may help decide which of the two different points of view on the Meissner effect discussed here is correct.

Consider a simply connected superconductor with a small cavity totally enclosed in its interior, as shown in Figs. 22 and 23. We show a spherical body with a spherical cavity, but the discussion here should apply to any simply connected body with a small cavity of any shape that is completely enclosed within the body. We assume the dimensions of the cavity are much smaller than the dimensions of the body.

The system is cooled in the presence of a small magnetic field. Will the field be completely expelled?

The state shown on the right panel of Fig. 22 has currents circulating only near the outer surface of the body and the magnetic field is completely expelled. This is the lowest energy state of the system.

Instead, the state shown on the right panel of Fig. 23 has the same currents circulating near the outer surface of the body as in Fig. 22, and additionally has currents circulating around the cavity and around a cylindrical region that extends from the bottom to the top of the body. In this cylindrical region the system is in the normal state. This state is *not* the lowest energy state of the system.

In the state shown on the right panel of Fig. 23 the magnetic field is trapped in the cavity and the cylindrical regions above and below it. The system cannot evolve to the lowest energy state shown in Fig. 22 right panel because this would require magnetic field lines to move across superconducting regions, which is not allowed. That is clear.

It is also clear that the state shown on the right panel of Fig. 22 can be reached by first cooling the system into the superconducting state in the absence of magnetic field and then applying the magnetic field. That is the same situation discussed in Sect. VIII, Fig. 3 panels **a** and **b**.

What is not clear [107] is whether the state shown on the right panel of Fig. 22 can ever be achieved under any cooling protocol, starting in the normal state in the presence of a magnetic field. One could try different cooling protocols [108], for example lowering the temperature first near the center of the body, or in the region near the cavity, or near the surface of the body; cooling at different rates, for example lowering the temperature very quickly so the system would supercool to a temperature much lower than T_1 with the applied $H = H_c(T_1)$. Or cooling very slowly hoping to avoid that the system gets stuck in metastable states. Or combining inhomogeneous temperature distribution patterns and rates of cooling in a variety of ways.

We argue that within the ‘emergent point of view’ discussed in this paper, there is no reason why there could not be a cooling protocol that would lead the system to evolve from the initial state on the left panel of Fig. 22 to the final state on the right panel of Fig. 22, which is the lowest energy state of the system. It is generally believed within that point of view that systems will “find a way” to reach their lowest energy state, as discussed earlier. The system shown in Fig. 22 right panel is described by a macroscopic wavefunction $\psi(\vec{r}) = n_s^{1/2}(\vec{r})e^{i\theta(\vec{r})}$ that is macroscopically phase coherent, the phase of $\psi(\vec{r})$ is the same at every point in the material. Of course inside the cavity the phase is undefined because there is no material. There is nothing in BCS theory, Ginzburg-Landau theory, time-dependent Ginzburg-Landau theory, nor the Higgs mechanism, that says that such a macroscopic quantum state cannot emerge in such a many-body system with quintillions of interacting particles, given that ‘more is different’ [35, 56, 57]. Minimization of the Ginzburg-Landau free energy of the system shown in Fig. 22 certainly leads to the state shown on the right panel of Fig. 22 and not to the one on the right panel of Fig. 23.

Instead, within the ‘reductionist point of view’ discussed in this paper, the final state will necessarily be the ‘metastable state’ shown on Fig. 23 right panel, the lowest energy state of Fig. 22 right panel cannot be reached starting from the system in the normal state with magnetic field in the interior [109]. In essence, this is simply because within that point of view expulsion of magnetic field requires radial charge flow, and there cannot be radial charge flow inside the cavity because there is no material there. If the magnetic field cannot be expelled from the cavity those magnetic field lines have to carve a path through the material to reach the outside of the body, paying the energy cost of destroying the superconductivity in their path.

An interesting consequence of this physics predicted by the reductionist viewpoint [110] is that the reverse process to that shown in Fig. 22, i.e. from the right panel to the left panel, will necessarily involve dissipation of some Joule heat, no matter how slowly it takes place, simply because the process is *irreversible*. Instead, within the ‘emergent’ viewpoint the process is reversible, so no Joule heat would be dissipated in either direction.

We note that these tests could also be performed with a rapidly rotating body that is cooled into the superconducting state in the absence of applied fields. If the ‘emergent’ point of view is correct, the resulting magnetic field should be perfectly uniform in the interior of the body including the cavity and given by the value Eq. (65). For a spinning sphere, the resulting magnetic moment (‘London moment’ [28]) would be precisely

$$m = \frac{m_e c}{e} \omega R^3 \quad (79)$$

for a sphere of radius R spinning with angular velocity ω , irrespective of whether the sphere has a cavity in its

interior or not. Instead, if the ‘reductionist’ point of view is correct, the magnetic field should be suppressed in a cylindrical region that goes through the cavity, and the resulting London moment would be smaller than Eq. (79), and smaller than what would result if the sphere is first cooled and then put into spinning motion, which would be Eq. (79).

In summary, experimental tests such as discussed in this section and similar ones [111] could rule out the ‘reductionist viewpoint’ if it is found that processes such as the one shown in Fig. 22 can take place in nature. Or, they could lend support to it if it is found that they cannot.

XXII. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

In this paper we have reviewed two different ways to understand the Meissner effect, the most fundamental property of superconductors.

In one way, which we called the ‘emergent point of view’, which is the overwhelmingly generally accepted point of view, there is no need to understand in detail the processes involved in the Meissner effect. Given a theory that describes the superconducting state with magnetic field excluded as the lowest energy state of the system, it is postulated that the system will find a way to reach this lowest energy state. The Meissner effect is a *consequence* of this fact. Within this point of view, here is no point in asking further questions [58, 59]. The conventional theory of superconductivity is such a theory.

However, we argue that there is experimental evidence that in our view casts strong doubt on the validity of this point of view. Namely, the fact that it is *extremely easy* for systems to *not* completely expel magnetic fields. In the real world the degree of magnetic field expulsion is extremely dependent on the purity of samples and is never complete, even for extremely pure samples [31–33]. This flies in the face of the article of faith that systems know how to reach their lowest energy state: in the presence of impurities or defects, magnetic field remains trapped, turning parts of the sample that would prefer to be superconducting normal, which costs energy compared to the state where the entire field is excluded [109]. Why doesn’t the system find its way to its lowest energy state?

In an alternative way to understand the Meissner effect, which we called the ‘reductionist point of view’, exposed within the theory of hole superconductivity [61], it is thought that it is necessary to understand the dynamics of the processes involved, which forces cause which processes, how momentum transfers between different parts of the system occur, what constraints are imposed by the fact that systems need to obey conservation laws and the laws of thermodynamics, what constraints are imposed by Bohr’s correspondence principle and the principles of magnetohydrodynamics, and what physical elements should the system possess to allow it to undergo

these processes. This understanding poses constraints on which systems can be superconducting and which cannot. In particular, it says that if the system does not have normal carriers with negative effective mass at the Fermi energy, it cannot reversibly interchange momentum between electrons and the body as a whole, which is necessary for the Meissner effect and its reverse to occur, hence such a system would not be a superconductor.

The crucial difference between both points of view, which should be amenable to experimental verification, is whether or not there is radial charge flow associated with the motion of magnetic field lines in the Meissner effect. Within the emergent point of view there isn't, within the reductionist point of view there is. Within the emergent point of view, charge carriers acquire azimuthal momentum spontaneously in the process of nucleation and growth of the superconducting phase in the presence of a magnetic field. Within the reductionist point of view, azimuthal momentum is a result of radial momentum plus the Lorentz force. As discussed in this paper, the mechanical momentum that needs to be transferred between electrons and ions during the Meissner effect is many orders of magnitude larger than the physical momentum of the supercurrent in the final state, so to understand how it happens is essential.

For classical conducting fluids, magnetohydrodynamics dictates that motion of magnetic field lines is closely associated with motion of the fluid. Within the emergent point of view, that physics is irrelevant to the Meissner effect. Within the reductionist point of view, it plays a key role.

We have pointed out that the Meissner effect and its reverse are understood to be *reversible processes* in an ideal situation, which implies that the entropy of the universe should not change in the processes [24]. This requires an explanation of how mechanical momentum is transferred between electrons and ions in a reversible way, since the Meissner current carries mechanical momentum. Within the reductionist approach discussed here, transfer of momentum between electrons and ions is mediated by the electromagnetic field, and no scattering processes are involved. For this to be possible requires radial motion of charge, to give rise to radial electric fields and associated electromagnetic azimuthal momentum. Within the emergent approach there is no radial motion of charge, which implies that there is no azimuthal electromagnetic field momentum, which implies that the electromagnetic field does not mediate the momentum transfer between electrons and ions. How such momentum transfer occurs without generation of entropy within the emergent point of view requires an explanation.

Within the emergent point of view, the physical process by which a quantum particle spontaneously acquires azimuthal momentum in opposition to the Faraday electric force acting on it is not specified, it would be something unique to the superconducting transition. A. Nikulov has attempted to provide a physical justification for it by postulating that there is an azimuthal

FIG. 24: Schematic explanation for why phase coherence is required in the superconducting phase (S) due to expansion of the orbits discussed in the text and not in the normal (N) phase. The black dots represent the position of the electron in its orbit, and its angular position is the ‘phase’.

“quantum force” that acts in the process [112, 113]. This quantum force would be a new force of nature that acts in no other physical situation and has no classical counterpart. In addition, it requires that there is another quantum force that is equal and opposite and acts azimuthally on the ions, so that momentum is conserved. We argue that these requirements make this point of view highly implausible.

Within the reductionist point of view, a physical process by which a quantum particle spontaneously acquires radial momentum is not difficult to conceive. Quantum particles lower their quantum kinetic energy by expanding their wavefunction [63], so they will do so if a constraint preventing it from happening is removed. The constraint that does not allow electrons in the normal phase to expand their wave function is that the superconducting phase requires *phase coherence*, because the resulting wavefunctions / orbits in the many-electron system will overlap, as shown in Fig. 24. Above the transition temperature the higher entropy of the normal phase, where each electron has its own individual random phase, dominates, and the free energy $F = E - TS$ is lowest. Below the transition temperature the superfluid electrons are willing to pay the entropy cost entailed in all having the same quantum phase required by the overlapping orbits (Fig. 24) because TS is smaller when T is lower, and the lowering of quantum kinetic energy achieved by wavefunction/orbit expansion dominates. Therefore, orbits will expand and overlap, driven by a real force, namely quantum pressure.

If the first point of view discussed here (emergent) is right, the second point of view is wrong. If the second point of view discussed here (reductionist) is right, the first point of view is wrong. There is no room for compromise.

What are the larger implications of this? If the emergent point of view is correct, it poses no constraints

on mechanisms giving rise to superconductivity. The electron-phonon interaction for conventional superconductors, and any of the myriad of pairing mechanisms that have been proposed for unconventional superconductors arising from correlated electron physics, remain plausible candidates to explain the superconductivity of known materials [114] and materials to be discovered. Within this prevailing point of view, the most promising way to achieve high temperature superconductivity is with materials with light atoms, and much effort is currently focused in that direction [115].

If the reductionist point of view discussed here is correct, it poses strict constraints on mechanisms of superconductivity. It implies that the electron-phonon interac-

tion is not the mechanism giving rise to superconductivity in any material [116, 117], instead superconductivity originates in electron-hole asymmetric electron-electron interactions that lower the kinetic energy of carriers upon pairing and requires that the normal state carriers have hole-like character. Within that point of view, the most promising way to achieve high temperature superconductivity is with materials containing negative anions in close proximity with hole conduction through them, like the high T_c cuprates and MgB_2 .

Therefore, for the physics community to determine what is the correct way to understand the Meissner effect in superconductors is urgent and important.

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